

Microplastics in Arctic waters of the Finnish Sámi area

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Inclusion of indigenous people is important in scientific work to assure the indigenous people's needs and rights.
- Microplastic concentrations in the waters of the Finnish Sámi area range from 45 to 423 MPs m⁻³.
- Microplastics should be monitored in the Finnish Sámi area.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

We explored the presence of microplastics in the Finnish Arctic Sámi home area. A dialogue between Indigenous knowledge and scientific field work produced data about microplastics in remote wilderness aquatic ecosystems. Methods included geographical Indigenous knowledge analysis, water sampling with fraction filtration, and imaging Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The MPs found were small; the mean particle size was $126 \pm 121 \mu\text{m}$. Particle concentrations of MPs in freshwater and marine samples varied between 45 and 423 MPs m⁻³ and the most common polymer types were polyethylene, polypropylene, and polyethylene terephthalate. In conclusion, because microplastics are present even in the wilderness areas, their abundance should be monitored to assess plastic pollution in the relatively pristine Arctic environments. Sámi Indigenous knowledge proved to be a beneficial and important initiator, because locals recognize the possible sources and transport pathways of plastic litter, and practical sampling sites in the complex freshwater systems of the area.

1. Introduction

The study of Arctic microplastics (MPs) has been advancing in recent years, especially in the marine environments and Polar ecosystems

(Bergmann et al., 2022; PAME, 2019). Yet, most of the region is underreported, especially in the context of freshwater environments and terrestrial catchment areas. National and regional agencies have been unable or incapable to detect or monitor the presence of microplastics in

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remote ecosystems. Also, the meaning and significance of potential presence of MPs to Arctic Indigenous peoples who are reliant on fish, game animals and other local food sources has been largely unknown. Meanwhile, many other issues and indicative processes, such as studies of persistent organic pollutants, have included the participation of northern communities and their lifeways and established co-produced monitoring regimes (Arctic Council, 2013). Microplastic abundances in water have been sampled and analysed in the Inuit areas of Northern Canada in a collaboration between scientists and local Indigenous people (Liboiron et al., 2021). Liboiron et al. (2021) use term “reconciliation science” which means that rights of Indigenous peoples are recognized and respected, when studies are conducted in their home areas. The reconciliation is a timely topic especially in Canada, where government and society have discriminated against the Indigenous peoples for example through forced assimilation, land theft, and positioning First Nations and Inuit peoples as subjects of research. Wong et al. (2020) list 10 calls to action in their article for natural scientists working in Canada. They do this to ensure that the rights of Indigenous peoples are respected.

Use of Indigenous knowledge in Finland is still a rather underused method in environmental monitoring. Yet, internationally it has been confirmed to be able to add to back casting, i.e. baselines of change in locations where very few previous science records exist (Burch, 2013; Mustonen and Feodoroff, 2013), to convey information about cultural indicator species and interconnections that have been unknown to science but are present for example in the local linguistic diversity (Frainer et al., 2020; Pecl et al., 2017) and to offer novel monitoring and interpretative frames (Johnson et al., 2015; Mustonen, 2015; Watson and Huntington, 2008). In this study we utilize indigenous knowledge following the 10 calls to action listed by Wong et al. (2020) to study microplastics in the area.

Microplastics are commonly defined as plastic particles with size smaller than 5 mm (GESAMP, 2016), or between 1 µm and 1 mm (Hartmann et al., 2019). MPs consist mainly of synthetic polymers insoluble to water, and they decompose very slowly in the environment. In addition, MPs contain plastic additives and non-intentionally added substances (NIAS), which may be harmful in the environment. The concentrations of MPs should be monitored, because MPs can cause adverse effects to aquatic organisms (Anbumani and Kakkar, 2018; Lambert et al., 2017; Prokić et al., 2019).

Concentrations of MPs have been reported for the ice and waters of the Arctic Ocean. The reported regions cover the Arctic Ocean quite well; samples have been taken from the North Pole region (Obbard et al., 2014), western coast of Greenland (Rist et al., 2020), the Arctic Ocean and the Greenland Gyre (Hänninen et al., 2021), the Eurasian Arctic (Yakushev et al., 2021), the Central Arctic Basin (Kanhai et al., 2018), the Fram Strait (Tekman et al., 2020), arctic sea ice (Peeken et al., 2018) and the eastern Canadian arctic waters (Huntington et al., 2020). There are also signs that plastic pollution has already surpassed the planetary boundary, meaning that plastics oppose a threat to Earth System processes (MacLeod et al., 2021; Persson et al., 2022). However, Arctic freshwater environments have not been studied comprehensively, as MPs have, to our knowledge, been analysed only from the sediments and waters of two lakes in Svalbard (González-Pleiter et al., 2020, 2021; Luoto et al., 2019), from Siberian rivers (Frank et al., 2021; Yakushev et al., 2021) and Lake Baikal (Karnaukhov et al., 2022; Moore et al., 2022). Microplastics of air in the northern Atlantic (Goßmann et al., 2023) and French Pyrenees (Allen et al., 2019) have also been studied, as air is supposedly a major source of plastics in remote areas. Atmospheric deposition of MPs is also closely related to MPs in snow as shown by Bergmann et al. (2019). However, the knowledge of abundances of MPs in the Arctic freshwaters, in both surface and depths, is lacking.

The first warning signs of MPs in Näättämö basin were reported by the Skolt Sámi co-researchers (Feodoroff, 2021; Watson and Huntington, 2008). This led the present process to unfold in ways that included the full inclusion of Indigenous knowledge and science. The early results

were also taken back to the affected communities (Mustonen et al., 2021) and to the Indigenous Sámi Parliament to stress the methods of Free, Prior and Informed Consent – FPIC (Brattland and Mustonen, 2018).

In this article, we present results from a three-year mission that documented the concentrations and polymer types of microplastics in interconnected freshwater and marine ecosystems in the Finnish Sámi home area and in the Barents Sea fjord ecosystem (Mustonen et al., 2021). The field sampling focused on the lake Inarijärvi, Näättämö river catchment and the Neiden fjord in the Barents Sea.

The hypothesis was that MPs would be present in waters of the study area, but to relatively lower extent than in more densely populated areas. Additionally, the help of indigenous people is also beneficial when selecting sampling sites and studying prevalence of emerging contaminants, such as microplastics.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Selection of the sampling areas

The choices of the sampling locations (Fig. 1) were based on the Skolt Sámi Indigenous knowledge observations (Mustonen et al., 2021) and concern of presence of potential microplastics pollution in the wilderness ecosystems of the Näättämö river. Main concerns included impact on salmonid fish and their quality (important for food security), human health for the people harvesting fish on the river and the overall status of the river system. The expected locations had been reported earlier by Sámi River Guardians as a part of the monitoring work on the river – for example visual observations of plastic pollution and ghost nets had triggered concern among the local community people (Mustonen, 2015). The topic had been present for several years in the Sevettijärvi village meetings as a source of concern. Based on this initial framing, a science team from University of Eastern Finland and Snowchange Cooperative (an Arctic community-based NGO) conducted three rigorous field campaigns in the pilot locations.

Overall for the research field work we followed the recent Arctic Council's (2020) *Toolbox for Comprehensive Plastics Monitoring in the Arctic* and AMAP Litter and microplastics monitoring guidelines (AMAP, 2021).

2.2. Sampling methods

In total, 23 freshwater and 2 marine samples were collected over three sampling periods. Samples S1-S9 were collected between the 15th and 18th of July 2021, samples S10-S18 between the 15th and 17th of October 2021 and samples S19-S25 between 31st of July and 2nd of August 2023. All the samples taken in 2023 were from the same sites as in 2021. Samples S1-S7, S10-S16 and S19-S25 are from the catchment area of Näättämö river, S8 and S9 from Lake Inarijärvi, and S17 and S18 from Näättämönvuono/Neiden Fjord (Fig. 1). Coordinates of sampling sites and exact sampled volumes are reported in the open data related to this article (Soininen et al., 2023), and detailed description of sampling equipment are reported in the Supplementary Materials.

Sampling was conducted by pumping water to a cascade-like filtration tube, equipped with three stainless-steel filters (Spinea Ltd) with diameters of 80 mm and different pore sizes: 315 µm, 100 µm and 50 µm. River and lake samples were taken approximately 1 m from the shore, and sea water samples were taken from a glass fibre boat, about 3 m from the side of the boat. River and lake samples were taken from a depth of around 30 cm below the surface, and ocean samples from 1 m below surface. The volume per sample was 100–200 l which was achieved after approximately 10 min of pumping depending on the sample. In 2023 only the 50 µm filter was used on each site. Furthermore, in 2023 three replicate samples were taken from each site, compared to only one sample from most of the sites in 2021. After the filtration, filters were transferred from the tube to plastic containers, made from

Fig. 1. Locations of all sampling sites (A), Location in the Finnish Sami area (B), Table of all sampling sites and samples (C).

polypropylene (PP). Filters were stored in closed containers in between sampling and analysis.

The sampling system included a battery-powered centrifugal pump, made from plastic, mainly acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) and polyphenylene oxide (PPO). Moreover, samples were transferred through a hose made from black polyvinyl chloride (PVC), but the cascade-like tube and filters were all made from stainless steel. All hose connectors and valves were made of brass. Before and between taking the samples, the whole system was rinsed with ambient water without the filters for about 5 min. Moreover, the filters were rinsed with ambient water before installing them to the tube. The filtration tube, pump and hoses used are pictured in supplementary information (Figs. S1-S5).

2.3. Sample pre-treatment

Contamination was prevented in the laboratory by filtering all solutions before use through a stainless-steel filter (20 μm), working in a fume hood, and using only non-plastic equipment. All glassware and equipment were rinsed carefully with tap and ultrapure water before use.

All the samples were treated with hydrogen peroxide (30 % v/v) to dissolve excessive organic material. The three filters of one sample were carefully moved to a large beaker and the filter container was rinsed with 100 ml of H_2O_2 to the beaker. The beakers were kept in an incubator-shaker at 50 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h, covered with an aluminium foil.

After oxidation, the filters were rinsed with ultrapure water to the same beaker. The solution was then filtered to a steel filter with pore size

of 20 μm . This filter was then rinsed with ultrapure water to a 5 μm silver membrane filter (Sterlitech Co). The whole volume of a sample was filtered, except for samples S16 and S17, which required sub-sampling. They contained more sand than other samples, and only 31 % and 76 % of the original volume was filtered and analysed to prevent stacking of particles and clogging of the silver membrane filters.

2.4. FTIR imaging

Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectral maps were measured with an Agilent Cary 670/620 imaging FTIR spectrometer equipped with 128 \times 128 focal plane array (FPA) detector. The whole filter area (diameter 12 mm) was measured in reflection mode using 15 \times cassegrain objective, 8 cm^{-1} spectral resolution, 4 scans, 3800–800 cm^{-1} spectral range, and 5.5 μm pixel resolution, similarly as in Uurasjärvi et al. (2021a).

Spectra from FTIR were analysed using SiMPle software (Primpke et al., 2020a). SiMPle is a tool that allows automated spectral analysis from the imaged area by comparing each pixel's spectrum to reference spectra. SiMPle provides particle counts by polymer types, particle sizes, and estimated masses of particles, based on the estimated volume and density of a particle. The reference library consisted of polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polyamide (PA), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polystyrene (PS), acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polyurethane (PU), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), polyacrylonitrile (PAN) and natural polymers (cotton, proteins). The parameters for classification of polymers in siMPle were similar as in Uurasjärvi et al. (2021b). Thresholds for classifying different polymers were > 0.6 for most of the polymers. For PS a

threshold of 0.55 was used and for PE 0.7. Particle was categorized as fibre, if its longest dimension from siMPLE data was at least 10 times longer than the shortest dimension. However, as imaging FTIR is not accurate for detecting all fibers (Uurasjärvi et al., 2021b), the categorization by shape is approximate.

2.5. Quality control of microplastic quantitation

Three recovery samples were prepared from PS microbeads (NIST Traceable Size Standards, 100 μm). The stock solution of approximately 20 beads ml^{-1} was prepared to ultrapure water. About 20–30 ml (50 beads) of the stock solution was pipetted to a Petri dish, and the number of PS beads on the dish was counted with a light microscope. The beads were rinsed to a beaker, and the recovery samples were pre-treated and measured similarly than the water samples.

Mean recovery rate using FTIR was $59 \pm 4\%$ (mean \pm standard deviation) by particle count. However, recovery of PS beads is an approximation for all types of MPs, because environmental MPs differ from beads by material, size, and shape.

Three laboratory blank samples were prepared similarly to the water samples. Only difference was that the steel sampling filters were rinsed with tap water and ultrapure water in laboratory, instead of filtering natural waters through them. After rinsing, they were placed to plastic containers and further treated similarly than the water samples.

Furthermore, three control samples were prepared similarly to the water samples to assess possible contamination caused by sampling equipment. These samples were prepared in the laboratory by pumping 50 l of tap water from a 20-l steel container, that had been rinsed with tap water beforehand. Whenever the water level got too low, more water was poured to the container, until 50 l of water was pumped through. Only the 50 μm pore size filters were used for these samples.

In total, 9 MPs of 4 different polymer types (PP 3, PE 1, PET 4, and PS 1) were detected in three blank samples. Mean number of MPs in blanks was 3 ± 0.8 , from which the limit of detection (LOD) was calculated as

$$\text{LOD} = \text{Mean} + \text{SD} \cdot 3 = 3 + 0.8 \cdot 3 = 5.4$$

All samples contained more MPs than the LOD, which indicated that the findings were from the environment, not caused by laboratory contamination. Moreover, the control samples for sampling equipment showed similar results; we found a total of 5 PP, 1 PE, 2 PET, and 1 PS particles from the three control samples.

3. Results

3.1. Concentrations of microplastics

Particle concentrations of MPs varied between samples from 45 to 423 MPs m^{-3} (Fig. 2, Table 1). Estimated mass concentrations of all MP types varied between samples from 2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ to 488 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

Samples S1-S7 were collected in the summer 2021 from the catchment area of Näättämö river, and they contained an average of 104 MPs m^{-3} . Sample S3 (Kirakkakoski) had the smallest particle concentration 55 MPs m^{-3} and S7 (Vainosjoki) the highest 185 MPs m^{-3} . Samples S10-S16, collected in the fall of the same year from the catchment area of Näättämö river, contained 133 MPs m^{-3} on average. The smallest particle concentration 45 MPs m^{-3} was found from S10 (Härkälahti) and the highest 205 MPs m^{-3} from S14 (Vainosjoki). Samples S8 and S9 from Lake Inarijärvi, taken in the summer 2021, contained 185 MPs m^{-3} and 90 MPs m^{-3} , respectively. Neiden Fjord (Näättämövuono) was sampled in the fall, and sample S17 contained 99 MPs m^{-3} and S18 72 MPs m^{-3} . Hence, the particle concentrations of MPs were lower in the fjord compared to the catchment area of Näättämö river or Lake Inarijärvi, except sample S10 which contained the lowest concentration in fall 2021 samples. Samples from 2023 showed some of the highest concentrations of all the sampling rounds with highest concentration being 423 MPs m^{-3} on sample S21 (Opukasjärvi 2). Lowest concentration of 2023 (97 MPs m^{-3}) was measured from sample S24 (Kirakkakoski).

Fig. 2. Particle concentrations and estimated mass concentrations in all samples. Summer 2021 (A), fall 2021 (B) and summer 2023 (C).

Table 1

Sample volumes, count of microplastics per site and microplastic concentrations. In samples S2 and S19-S25, results are presented as averages of three replicate samples. ^aOn samples S16 and S17 the sampled volume was 200 l, but due to large amount of sand in the samples, sub-samples of 31 % and 76 % were analysed, respectively.

Sample	Coordinates ETRS-TM35FIN		Sample volume (l)	MPs per sample	Concentration (MPs m ⁻³)	Concentration (µg m ⁻³)
	N	E				
S1	7,720,028	566,498	120	7	58	15
S2	7,734,392	576,663	200	29 ± 7	117 ± 37	7 ± 3
S3	7,721,594	572,859	200	11	55	12
S4	7,709,606	560,724	200	15	75	30
S5	7,721,608	555,577	200	24	120	16
S6	7,722,199	555,060	200	24	120	19
S7	7,719,839	575,293	200	37	185	43
S8	7,682,208	550,483	200	18	90	13
S9	7,678,655	546,065	200	37	185	28
S10	7,712,055	563,173	200	9	45	2
S11	7,733,446	591,758	200	28	140	12
S12	7,710,385	562,415	200	21	105	11
S13	7,711,466	563,111	200	21	105	10
S14	7,719,658	575,907	200	41	205	26
S15	7,719,839	575,293	200	37	185	38
S16 ^a	7,720,255	574,673	62	9	145	3
S17 ^a	7,734,299	598,987	152	15	99	17
S18	7,734,602	599,473	180	13	72	12
S19	7,719,839	575,293	100	12 ± 0	117 ± 5	37 ± 13
S20	7,710,385	562,415	100	23 ± 7	233 ± 74	215 ± 251
S21	7,722,199	555,060	100	42 ± 10	423 ± 98	488 ± 245
S22	7,721,608	555,577	100	30 ± 13	300 ± 131	129 ± 21
S23	7,733,446	591,758	100	20 ± 6	203 ± 62	79 ± 52
S24	7,721,594	572,859	100	10 ± 1	97 ± 9	14 ± 7
S25	7,720,028	566,498	100	26 ± 11	263 ± 106	40 ± 16

Fig. 3. Polymer types in percentages by site. Summer 2021 (A), fall 2021 (B) and summer 2023 (C).

3.2. Polymer types and particle sizes

All 25 samples studied contained altogether 8 polymer types: PE, PP, PET, PS, PMMA, ABS, PA and PAN. Summer 2021 samples contained PP, PE, PET, PS, ABS and PMMA, and fall 2021 samples contained the same types, but also PA (Fig. 3.). Summer 2023 samples contained all 8 polymer types, except PMMA. Based on the number of particles, the most common polymer types were PP, PE and PET with proportions of 49.4 %, 18.6 % and 24.8 % in all the summer 2021 samples, and 59.8 %, 15.2 % and 9.4 % in all of the fall 2021 samples, respectively. Hence, the overall proportions of the three most common polymer types were 92.8 % in summer 2021 samples and 84.4 % in fall 2021. However, some differences were observed between the samples: sample S1 (Jäniskoski) did not contain PP, although it was common in all other samples. Moreover, the fall samples from Neiden Fjord (S17 and S18) contained a remarkably higher proportion of PE particles (42 %) than fall samples from the Näätämö river catchment area (6 %). Samples S7, S14-S16 and S19 were collected from Vainosjoki river, but they contained different shares of the plastic types. PP, PE and PET were also the most common polymer types in summer 2023 samples, with portions of 58.2 %, 30.5 % and 4.1 % respectively. Most notably in 2023, the portion of PET was lower, and PE was higher than during other sampling campaigns.

By shape, majority of MPs were classified as fragments; only 0.8 % of the MPs were fibers in summer 2021 samples and 2.1 % in fall 2021 samples. In summer 2023, 0.6 % of the microplastics were fibers.

Size distribution of the MPs was quite similar between summer and fall 2021 samples, with most of the particles being 20–150 μm in the longest dimension (Fig. 4). The mean particle size (mean \pm standard deviation) was $97 \pm 79 \mu\text{m}$ in summer 2021 samples, and $108 \pm 83 \mu\text{m}$ in fall 2021 samples. In summer 2023 samples the mean particle size was $148 \pm 146 \mu\text{m}$.

4. Discussion

In this study, the particle concentration of MPs varied between 45 and 450 MPs m^{-3} in all the samples. The mean particle concentration was $150 \pm 86 \text{MPs m}^{-3}$, and the median concentration was 120 MPs m^{-3} . Rist et al. (2020) took samples from a fjord in Nuuk, Greenland, with a principally similar pump and filtration system to this study, but retaining $>10 \mu\text{m}$ particles. The marine samples contained 67–278 MPs m^{-3} , with a median of 142 MPs m^{-3} . Tekman et al. (2020) sampled sea water at the HAUSGARTEN observatory retaining $>32 \mu\text{m}$ particles. Microplastic concentrations in HAUSGARTEN samples ranged from 9 to 1287 MPs m^{-3} with a mean concentration of $95 \pm 85 \text{MPs m}^{-3}$. Hence, the MP concentrations were in the same range in Greenland, HAUSGARTEN and Finnish Sámi areas. Most of the MPs were PE, PP, and PET and their particle size was smaller than 100 μm in both Greenland and the present study. The polymer types are the most produced and used ones. Hence, it is impossible to name any individual sources for certain.

The particle concentrations of MPs in water are not always straightforwardly comparable between studies, as methods may affect the results remarkably. For example, the sampling filter or net defines what is the smallest size of MPs to be retained, and the identification and/or quantitation method may also affect the lowest limit of size (Primpke et al., 2020b). It has also been shown that filters can significantly undercount fibers, because thin fibers can get through the filter pores (Frost and Bond, 2022). The abundance of MPs has been shown to increase while the size decreases, in different types of aquatic environments (Rist et al., 2020; Tekman et al., 2020; Uurasjärvi et al., 2020). The mean particle size of MPs found in this study was approximately 100 μm , indicating that particle concentrations would have been significantly lower if we would have sampled with for example 300 μm net instead of 50 μm . In addition, in this study we found particles smaller than 50 μm which is possible because microplastics can flock together

Fig. 4. Box and whiskers plot of particle sizes (the longest dimensions) of MPs. Summer 2021 (A), Fall 2021 (B), Summer 2023 (C). Sample set B contained one larger than 500 μm particle in sample S15. Set C also contained three larger than 1 mm particles. These particles were distributed between samples S20 (2) and S21 (1).

and detach from each other during sample treatment. The pore size we used for the filter can also result to the very low portion of fibers we found. Also, the measurement method for shape was not exact and it may have underestimated the number of fibers (Uurasjärvi et al., 2021b). This is because the fibers do not attach to the filter surface evenly; hence, the fibers are not in focus, and they get detected as many particles or not at all.

The sampling method allowed taking relatively large volumes. However, compared to the size of the studied water systems, these sample volumes represent only a small fraction of the whole system. Furthermore, samples S2 and S19-S25 were the only samples with 3 replicates. MPs as particulate analytes are not evenly distributed in a water body, but they may aggregate and accumulate to certain areas or depths, either coincidentally or seasonally. Hence, to get a more comprehensive view of the levels of MP pollution in a certain area, samples should be taken periodically for a longer time interval. Furthermore, using only one filter instead of several ones, might lead to better yields. An indication to this is that in 2023 when using only a 50 µm pore size filters, we saw higher concentrations and bigger particles on average. It seems that particles might get stuck to the pores of the filters, and thus using only one filter per sample, higher amounts of bigger plastics are found. This behaviour would also explain our relatively low recovery rates, because the particles in these samples could also get stuck on the filters during treatment.

MP abundances in Arctic freshwaters have not been studied comprehensively yet, but >300 µm MP fibers have been found in sediments of Svalbard (González-Pleiter et al., 2020). Surface water samples from Lake Baikal have been reported to contain 34–707 particles m⁻³ (Moore et al., 2022). Moreover, samples from Siberian rivers Tom and Ob have been reported to have average microplastic concentrations of 44.2 and 51.2 particles m⁻³, respectively (Frank et al., 2021).

Weather conditions in different seasons may affect the abundance of MPs in water as winds, currents and dimictic overturn (complete mixing of the water, when the temperature is the same in the whole water body) may cause sediment resuspension, which can release sedimented MPs back to the water (Vaughan et al., 2017). During the sampling in Neiden Fjord, wind blew heavily from the north towards the end of the fjord and the mouth of Näätamö river. Therefore, the origin of the sampled microplastics is not certain.

Nevertheless, rivers, lakes, sea, and the atmosphere are interconnected in the environment, and especially the lightest and smallest MPs may be long-range transported (Horton and Dixon, 2018). Hence, the sources of MPs are rarely possible to track and identify. However, the most important sources have been estimated to be traffic, inefficient waste management, littering (intentionally and unintentionally), wastewater, and fragmentation of large plastic litter in the environment (GESAMP, 2016; Horton and Dixon, 2018).

The largest village in the study area is Sevettijärvi, with population of around 350 (Mustonen and Feodoroff, 2013). In addition to the permanent residents, the area is popular among tourists, especially for fishing and hiking. The area does not have large-scale industry, which could release MP and the amount of treated wastewater effluent discharged to the waters is very small compared to more populated areas. Therefore, we can deduce that the major local source of MPs in the area could be fragmentation of MPs from large plastic items in the environment, released by intentional or unintentionally littering, such as lost fishing gear, protective plastic wrapping of reindeer feeding fodder or food packages from hikers. Beyond the local sources, long-range atmospheric transportation of MPs can cause accumulation of MPs to even very remote arctic areas (Bergmann et al., 2019; Evangelidou et al., 2020).

Arctic natural ecosystems are often considered to be in the best natural condition out of world's functioning biogeographical regions (Arctic Council, 2013). Whilst industrial activities have affected some northern locations, large interconnected systems between the oceans, freshwater systems and terrestrial sites provide ecosystem services and

functions in many ways less disturbed than in more southern locations. Yet, earlier research (Arctic Council, 2020) has already found that overall presence of MPs in the Arctic and both climate change (Pecl et al., 2017) and environmental pollution are causing changes in the Arctic as an interconnected location.

4.1. Role of indigenous knowledge in the study

Brattland and Mustonen (2018) reviewed the role of Indigenous knowledge of the region. Their determination was that much of the Indigenous knowledge in the region is still, despite some high-level (Arctic Council, 2013) recognitions for the most part, unknown, underutilized and/or undervalued in the Nordic environmental monitoring missions as a method. They agree with Huntington et al. (2017) who stress the agency (i.e. who does the work) and the capacity (i.e. mechanisms to be able to carry out novel monitoring and observations, see Johnson et al. (2015). This research builds on their framing to increase the monitoring capacities along the river.

Within the similar framework as Berkes (2018) and positively engaging with the Indigenous peoples but in Finland and Norway, we analysed microplastics in river and lake waters in collaboration with the Skolt Sámi Indigenous communities in the Näätamö river basin and with Sámi and local communities in the lake Inari and Neiden fjord geographies. These efforts have been a part of the Sámi-initiated Näätamö river collaborative management efforts since 2011 (Mustonen and Feodoroff, 2013; Pecl et al., 2017). Therefore, we have implemented Free, Prior and Informed Consent in this research all along. The Sámi were asked through community workshops and individual meetings priorities of research. Microplastics monitoring rose as one of the top priorities in the Näätamö area (Mustonen et al., 2021). It was building on Sámi-led efforts of 'visual histories' (Mustonen, 2015) that had detected arrival of new species and changes in the ecosystems caused by climate change. Skolt Sámi co-researchers were initiators of the present study (Mustonen and Feodoroff, 2013) and have contributed their consented, essential Indigenous knowledge into the paper. We position and have invited Sámi knowledge holders to be co-authors of the present paper to strengthen the implementation of the role of Indigenous knowledge in the work (see on co-production as a method for example at Berkes, 2018).

As Feodoroff (2021) points out, the engagement that Indigenous peoples, in this case, the Skolt Sámi, especially women, have with their home areas and landscapes is extremely sensitive and relevant for observation of environmental changes. Feodoroff (2021) highlights the female bodily commitment, i.e. the interconnection of Indigenous landscapes and peoples as well as their multi-sensory perception (also in Berkes (2018)) as mechanisms to detect change (Johnson et al., 2015; Watson and Huntington, 2008).

Our research findings strengthen the interconnectedness of plastic pollution across the sea into freshwater systems. Not all plastic pollution discovered now for the first time in the European North originates in the region; it may be carried by transboundary pollution and in theory be sourced also from the oceans, accumulating in the anadromous fish returning for spawning in Näätamö system. This is in line with the autonomous agency (Huntington et al., 2017) that led the Sámi to act and establish partnerships with science to position and assess these novel discoveries.

Indigenous Sámi knowledge (Brattland and Mustonen, 2018), especially of Sámi women (Feodoroff, 2021) provided centrally important to our inquiry being the people who initiated the study concept due to their concern and observations of the river. In this case we can see that the novel, undefined but robust and culturally vital space and methodology of Sámi knowledge produced novel discoveries and balanced dialogue with science and research. As Johnson et al. (2015) point out the role of Indigenous knowledge holders in community-based monitoring activities is crucial.

The Sámi home area, *Sápmi*, is considered often to be one of the most

unpolluted areas in Europe (Arctic Council, 2013). Much in line with global research (see for example Frainer et al., 2020) Indigenous home areas are maintaining 80 % of the world's remaining biodiversity – this is also true in the Sámi homelands, where the remaining boreal natural forests, endemic salmonid fish, several dozen Arctic bird species and many other critically important species can be found in relatively undisturbed living spaces (Arctic Council, 2013). Lastly the boreal and the Arctic contain one third of the world's remaining soil-based carbon, making it central in functioning terms in the fight against climate change.

4.2. Significance of plastic discovery in context

Our discovery of MPs in the European North is significant in two ways – first it confirms the expected and theorized presence of MPs in the freshwater and fjord ecosystems and second, it relied on Indigenous knowledge – science dialogue in a sustained and balanced manner that was used during the two years of work.

We now know that whilst MPs have been present, we have been able to quantify their amounts for the first time. Although microplastic amounts remain relatively low, we have discovered them even in the most remote wilderness areas of the Sámi space and we know that these aquatic and terrestrial basins are interconnected with the global problems of plastic pollution and impacts. On the other hand, only through the well-conducted monitoring and observational actions we can start to assess and formulate responses to these pressing issues of our time (Johnson et al., 2015).

While the Sámi, with marginalised power and resources, were the primary actors in conducting this science-Indigenous knowledge study to its end they are not positioned yet well to address the sourcing of the pollution (Huntington et al., 2017). If we try to draft some recommendations for policy options based on the discoveries and results of our work, we can highlight some priorities.

First, a well-funded monitoring of MPs using both science and Indigenous knowledge should be installed with priority for those ecological hotspots such as Teno, Näättämö, Ponoj and other remaining relatively pristine basins in the Barents area. Projects may be able to produce similar novel discoveries but only through the rigorous monitoring of the whole context, extent and scope of the problem may be understood.

Second, where applicable, control, collection and prevention of plastic pollution and waste should be prioritized in the Sámi home area. We need to remember as Huntington et al. (2017) reminds us that the Indigenous people world-wide are often not the initiators of environmental pollution and problems – rather they are in the front lines of suffering from the consequences of global society and economy. The addressing of the waste should include all aspects of the northern society and human-induced drivers – the urban centres, residential and tourist housing, economic activities such as forestry, reindeer herding, fisheries, infrastructure and road development, tourism, and other relevant contexts. This may take the form of developing better plastic recycling sites, waste collection locations, filtering of plastics waste on wastewater systems and other technical aspects of prevention. Ranger-style patrols to collect plastics left by outsider tourists and other visitors is a very cost-effective and early prevention at source especially in the wilderness areas of Kaldoaivi, Våtsäri and other strategic locations.

Third, steps proposed in the Arctic Council (2020) “A Toolbox for Comprehensive Plastics Monitoring in the Arctic” should be taken into the regional environmental authorities and offered as a model of implementation on a strategy of microplastics monitoring and prevention. As before for example in the Arctic Council's and UN work on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) in early 2000s (Arctic Council, 2013, see also <http://www.pops.int/TheConvention/Overview/TextoftheConvention/tabid/2232/Default.aspx>) we need to advance the action on MP associated pollution in the Arctic as a transboundary and international phenomenon, one that is at the same time impacting the

local, often Indigenous home areas and simultaneously is a global and quickly proliferating pollution problem.

Microplastics are a new, novel problem in the high latitudes. Both the ecosystems and the unique Indigenous societies, such as the Sámi, and other local communities, have an inherent value and right to exist and choose their own pathways. These locations are also greatly stressed by rapidly proceeding climate change impacts expected to worsen. Arctic Councils (2020) “A Toolbox for Comprehensive Plastics Monitoring in the Arctic” demonstrates good steps towards linking a systematic monitoring of MPs and their consequences in the region. In addition to monitoring, we need action, now, and in effective and cross-cutting ways to preserve, protect and maintain the Arctic as plastic-free as possible. Indigenous knowledge and peoples, as also in this case, have often been at the vanguard of being early responders and detection teams when new threats and pollution issues have emerged. They need to be centred and fully included also in future MP actions in the region.

5. Conclusions

Microplastics are present in waters of the remote Finnish Sami areas. The particle concentrations were on the same magnitude as in other arctic areas, such as the Siberian rivers Tom and Ob. Moreover, the plastic types were commonly used materials, such as polyethylene, polypropylene, and polyethylene terephthalate. The local collaboration proved beneficial at the selection of the sampling sites, considering both scientific interest and practical arrangements. Most importantly, the collaborative study produces information, which is needed by the local community. Arctic areas are especially vulnerable to climate change and plastic pollution due to the pristine and undisturbed nature of many ecosystems. Both climate change and plastic pollution affect the nature-based living of local communities. To prevent harmful changes and enhance the ability of local communities to adapt the change, knowledge about the state of the environment is needed. In the case of plastic pollution, occurrence of large plastic litter and microplastics should be measured in the Arctic areas to monitor the state of the environment. Whilst all locations need to be monitored the remote and undisturbed nature in the Arctic point to a special role of observations for these remaining wilderness ecosystems.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Tuomo Soininen: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Emilia Uurasjärvi:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Lauri Hämäläinen:** Investigation. **Noora Huusari:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Jouko Moshnikoff:** Investigation. **Eetu Niiranen:** Visualization, Investigation. **Pauliina Feodoroff:** Investigation. **Tero Mustonen:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Arto Koistinen:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data has been made open and link can be found in the manuscript

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.173666>.

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